

Role Of Digital Marketing In Business Growth

Miss. Bhavana Santosh Kenjale

PG Student, Rayat Shiksha Sanstha's Savitribai Phule Mahil Mahavidyalaya, Satara

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15130860

Abstract:

In modern days of information explosion, digital marketing has become highly influencing factor which has revolutionized the business and its marketing strategy as well. The digital marketing has become an essential ingredient of the business growth in India. The role of digital marketing and of content marketing specifically is a huge help to leverage some free advertising and helps in business growth. Digital marketing makes it simple to target your exact customers. Focusing on your specific target customers increases both customer satisfaction and revenue.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Marketing Strategy, Content Marketing, Customer Satisfaction, Online Marketing.

Introduction:

Digital marketing is the component of marketing that uses the internet and online based digital technologies such as desktop computers, mobile, phones and other digital media and platforms to promote products and services. It has significantly transformed the way brands and businesses utilize technology for marketing since the 1990s and 2000s. As digital platforms became increasingly incorporated into marketing plans and everyday life, and as people increasingly used digital devices instead of visiting physical shops, digital marketing campaigns have become prevalent, employing combinations of methods. Some of these methods include, Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Search Engine Method (SEM), content automation, campaign marketing, Data-driven marketing, ecommerce marketing, social media marketing, social media optimization, e-mail direct marketing, display advertising, e-books, and optical disks and games. Digital Marketing extends to non-internet channels that provides digital media, such a television, Mobile

Phones SMS and MMS, Callbacks, and on-hold mobile ringtons. The extension to non-internet channels differentiates digital marketing from online marketing,

Purpose:

This Paper seeks to importance of various aspects of Digital Marketing Like
Brand Awareness
Content Marketing
Create a budget
Increases Sale

Benefits Of Digital Marketing:

1. Brand Awareness:
Digital Marketing helps businesses reach a wider audience and increase brand recognition.
2. Customer Engagement:
Digital Marketing helps businesses engage with customers and get real-time feedback.
3. Cost-Effectiveness:
Digital Marketing can be more cost-effective than traditional marketing.
4. Return on Investment:

Digital Marketing can help businesses increase their return on investments.

Types of Digital Marketing:

- Search Engine Optimization: SEO Helps Businesses rank higher in search engine results
- Search Engine Marketing:- SEM Helps Businesses market through search engine.
- Social Media Marketing:- Helps Businesses engage with cutomers on social media.
- Pay-Per-Click Advertising:- Helps Businesses reach a targeted audience by paying per click on their advertising.
- Content Marketing:- Helps businesses create content to engage with customers
- Email Marketing:- Helps businesses send targeted messages to customers via email.

Design /Methodology:

1. Collection of Data on Google form survey through questionnaire.
2. To take few samples of whole collective data.
3. Analysis of samples through basic statistical terminology like Mean, median, mode.
4. To find out the conclusion of analysis in terms of rate percent through study of their pie-charts and graphs accordingly.

Google Form Questionnaire Information Graph/Piachart:

Tabular Format (Statistical Terminology):

Factors	Proportion
Mean	5.4
Median	5
Mode	10

Factors	Proportion
Mean	5.7142
Median	5
Mode	9

In above Situation approximately as per our data collection Facebook and Youtube platform use for collecting information and showing awareness among the digital platform.

Tabular Format (Statistical Terminology):

In above situation approximately as per our data collecting Influencer marketing platform use for collectiong information and make creative efforts among the digital platform.

Tabular Format (Statistical Terminology):

Factors	Proportion
Mean	5.5
Median	5
Mode	9

In above situation as per our data collecting video and blog opticals use for marketing strategy and create influencer environment enhance among the business.

Google Form link:

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScyHI3DdrDFdRp8uK5k9LbVbhV3ice0MFs7eGsRmHLCyp9EyA/viewform?usp=header>

Approach / Objective:

1. To determine the basic proportion of Role of Digital Marketing in business growth through their sample of collective data.
2. To identify the quantitative aspects like mean, median, mode of collective data through their samples.

3. To analyze their spending money on Digital Marketing on daily, weekly, monthly, yearly basis.

Originality / Values:

To estimate the importance of various factors regarding our Digital Marketing form use of our business.

Result / Conclusion:

According to our statistical survey, almost 100% business man use of Instagram from Digital Marketing. Among the 50% choose business man purchased a product/service based on an online advertisement. Also 90% business man use of mobile marketing because there is most effective digital marketing channel. Almost 30% business man engage multiple times a day with our brand from social media and same of the 30% rarerly and never engage with our brand from social media. The business man is 90% video content prfer to consume on digital marketing platform.

Reference:

1. <https://www.springboard.com/blog/business-and-marketing/digital-marketing-importance/>
2. <https://www.sigmasolve.com/blog/digital-marketing-for-business/>